

Formulation Development Of Film Forming Spray Of *Tridax Procumbens*

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ABSTRACT

Wound healing is a complex biological process that is often delayed due to microbial infections at the site of injury. Topical drug delivery systems offer several advantages over conventional oral therapy by bypassing first-pass metabolism and providing localized, sustained drug release. The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a topical film-forming herbal spray containing *Tridax procumbens* Linn., a medicinal plant known for its antimicrobial and wound-healing properties. Ethanolic extract of *Tridax procumbens* leaves was prepared by cold maceration and evaluated for antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Candida albicans* using the disc diffusion method. Film-forming sprays were formulated using different polymers such as Eudragit S100, HPMC, PVA, and HPC, along with suitable plasticizers and preservatives. The prepared formulations were evaluated for pH, volume per spray, drying time, spray angle, flexibility, stickiness, and washability. Among the formulations, F1 exhibited optimal film-forming ability, rapid drying time, acceptable spray angle, and good flexibility. The results indicate that *Tridax procumbens* film-forming spray is a promising topical formulation for effective wound healing and infection control.

Keywords: Film forming spray, *Tridax procumbens*, Wound healing, Excipients Optimization.

INTRODUCTION

In recent days, the therapy of wound and skin infections is evolving and becoming more effective through timely medication-related care. When biological tissues such as skin, mucous membrane, and other tissues are damaged, a wound is formed [1]. The risk of infection increases since the protective layer is damaged [2]. Delayed wound healing is often due to infection [3]. The topical delivery system bypasses first-pass metabolism and avoids the effects of the gastrointestinal tract and pharmacokinetics [4]. Transdermal drug delivery systems offer an effective approach to address the low bioavailability of many oral drugs, the pain and inconvenience of injections, and the limited controlled-release options of both [5]. There are numerous topical formulations such as patches, gels, lotions, creams, ointments, and sprays available in the market; however, novel systems are

being developed to overcome challenges related to permeation through the skin barrier [6].

The film-forming spray is a novel topical delivery system that provides delayed drug release and produces enhanced therapeutic effects [7&8]. This system improves wound healing properties and offers advantages such as transparency, non-greasiness, lower skin irritation, resistance to wipe-off, longer retention time, greater dosage flexibility, improved patient compliance, and better aesthetic appearance [9,10]. The main evaluation parameters of this formulation include drying speed, pH, viscosity, spray angle, tensile strength, and film integrity [11].

Tridax procumbens is a widespread weed and flowering plant with various medicinal properties. Traditionally, it has been used in India as an antimicrobial agent, insect repellent, and for treating

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various biological disorders [12]. *Tridax procumbens* has been found to be effective as an antimicrobial agent against *Pseudomonas vulgaris* [13]. It contains major constituents such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, phenols, saponins, carbohydrates, glycosides, and cardiac glycosides, among which flavonoids exhibit significant antimicrobial activity [14]. This plant shows potent wound healing activity in both diabetic and non-diabetic individuals [15]. The nozzle type, spray pressure, and nature of the liquid influence the atomization quality [16]. Selection of excipients is very important in film-forming spray formulations [17]. This research focuses on determining the wound healing activity of the ethanolic extract of *Tridax procumbens* and emphasizes the selection of suitable excipients such as polymers, solvents, plasticizers, and humectants to formulate an optimized film-forming spray for future commercialization.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Materials

The leaves of *Tridax procumbens* were collected from rural parts of Madurai. The ethanol was bought from Bharath Chemicals, India. Hypromellose (Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, 15 cPs) USP was bought from SD Fine Chemicals Ltd, India. Sucralose USP/NF was procured from the NutraSweet company, US. Ginger flavour was bought from Modern Scientific Lab, India. Glycerin was procured from Paxmy Speciality Chemicals, India.

1. Preparation of extracts by cold maceration method

The cold maceration method was used for extraction. Ethanolic extraction of *Tridax procumbens* was carried out as a batch process to obtain maximum phytoconstituents. Initially, 100 g (50 g × 2) of dried leaves were taken in 1000 ml beakers, and 500 ml of ethanol was poured into each beaker. The beakers were then covered with aluminium foil. The leaves were soaked in ethanol for 3 days with intermittent shaking. At the end of 3 days, the extract was filtered using muslin cloth. The same maceration process was repeated after loosening the marc remaining. At the end of 6 days, the extract was again filtered using muslin cloth, and the marc was strained to collect the

maximum constituents. The collected ethanolic extract was concentrated using a vacuum oven and further concentrated on a water bath.

2. Antimicrobial study by disk diffusion method

2.1. Preparation of agar medium

Agar medium was prepared from a commercially available dehydrated base according to the manufacturer's instruction. The required quantities of nutrient agar (5g for 100 ml) and nutrient broth (4 g for 100 ml) were prepared by dissolving it in distilled water in conical flasks. Media was sterilized in an autoclave at 15 psi pressure and 121°C for 15 min. After sterilization, nutrient agar media was poured aseptically into sterilized petriplates in a laminar flow hood. All the steps were performed in sterile environment in order to prevent contamination. The media was allowed to be solidified in petriplates for about an hour and then placed in an incubator at 37°C for 24 hrs. The next day, uncontaminated plates were used for culturing of the microorganisms. If plates are not to be immediately used, they may be stored in the refrigerator inside air tight plastic bags at 2-8°C.

Microorganism used for the antimicrobial activity

Antimicrobial activity was tested against the bacterial and fungal strains such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram- positive bacteria), *Proteus vulgaris* (Gram-negative bacteria) and *Candida albicans* (fungi). These microorganisms were selected due to their clinical relevance in skin and soft tissue infections and their common use in antimicrobial screening studies.

2.3. Standards used for the antimicrobial activity

Standard antimicrobial agents were employed as positive controls to validate the sensitivity of the test microorganisms and to provide a reference for comparing the activity of the plant extract. Linezolid (2 mg/ml) and Cefotaxime (1 mg/ml) were used as the standard antibacterial drugs against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram- positive bacteria) and *Proteus vulgaris* (Gram- negative bacteria), respectively, due to their broad-spectrum antibacterial activity. For the fungal strain *Candida albicans*, Fluconazole (2 mg/mL) was used as the standard antifungal agent.

2.2. Inoculating of petriplates

A sterile cotton swab was dipped into the standardized microbial suspension and used to inoculate the surface of the agar medium by evenly streaking the plate to obtain a uniform lawn of growth.

2.3. Disc preparation

Whatman filter paper discs were impregnated with the extract at two concentrations: a high concentration (2 mg/ml for Gram-positive bacteria, 1 mg/ml for Gram-negative bacteria, and 2 mg/ml for fungi) and a low concentration (1 mg/ml for Gram-positive bacteria, 0.5 mg/ml for Gram-negative bacteria, and 1 mg/ml for fungi). The discs were then aseptically picked up using sterile forceps and placed onto the previously inoculated and dried agar plates.

2.4. Incubation

The plates were incubated in an inverted position at 30 °C or at the optimum growth temperature of the test microorganism. The zones of inhibition were observed after 16 - 18 hours of incubation. Slow-growing organisms were incubated for a longer period.

3. Optimization of excipients in film-forming spray

Selection of suitable polymer and solvent system plays a critical role in a film forming spray. Safer, commonly used solvents for topical formulations, such as water and ethanol, were selected and used as solvents. Placebo trials were taken using polymers such as Polymethacrylate (Eudragit S100), Hypromellose (HPMC E15 & HPMC 3cps), hydroxyl propyl cellulose (Klucel EXF) and polyvinyl alcohol. Film forming spray with different combination and concentration of polymers were formulated and are tabulated below. Polyethyleneglycol-400 and glycerin were used as plasticizer and humectant respectively. Methylparaben and propylparaben were used as preservative to increase the shelf life of formulation. Based on the visual appearance of the spray and drying time, the most effective combination was finalized. The placebo trials taken are presented in Table 1.

Batchcode	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	
% of solvents used	Alcohol	100	20	50	80	100	50	50	50	50	50	66.6	66.6	66.6
	Water	0	80	50	20	0	50	50	50	25	25	33.3	33.3	33.3
Ingredients	mg / batch													
HPMC E15	1060	1020	1060	1020	490	700	700	700	-	700	1000	1200	-	
Eudragit S100	-	-	-	-	210	700	350	175	-	350	300	-	-	
Polyvinyl alcohol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	300	-	-	350	350	
HPMC 3cPs	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	100	-	
HPC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	300	-	-	-	1000	
Glycerin	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	
PEG 200	224	224	224	224	224	224	224	224	224	224	-	-	-	
PEG 400	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	224	224	224	
Methyl Paraben	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	50	50	
Propyl Paraben	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	50	50	

Ethanol	10ml	2ml	5ml	8ml	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml	2.5ml	2.5ml	10ml	10ml	10ml
Purified water	-	8ml	5ml	2ml	-	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml	20ml	20ml	30ml

4. Formulation of film-forming spray

In a beaker, 20 ml of purified water was taken. For dissolving Eudragit S100, the pH of the water was adjusted to 7 by the addition of 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution. To this weighed quantity of polymers were added and stirred in mechanical stirrer to get a homogenous solution ^[19]. 1 g of *Tridax procumbens* crude extract was dissolved in 10 ml of ethanol and added to the above prepared polymer

solution and stirred well. Methylparaben, Propylparaben, PEG-400 and glycerin were added to the prepared solution and sonicated for 15 minutes. The prepared solution was transferred to 30 ml of glass spray bottle. The composition of the *Tridax procumbens* film-forming spray formulation is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Formulation of *Tridax procumbens* film-forming spray

S.No	Batch code	F1	F2	F3
	Ingredients	Quantity/Batch		
1.	Crude extract of <i>Tridax Procumbens</i>	1g	1g	1g
2.	EudragitS 100	300mg	-	-
3.	Hypromellose (HPMC E15)	1000mg	1200mg	-
4.	Polyvinyl alcohol	-	350mg	350mg
5.	Hypromellose (HPMC 3cPs)	100mg	100mg	-
6.	Hydroxy propyl cellulose (Klucel EXF)	-	-	1000mg
7.	Propyl paraben	50mg	50mg	50mg
8.	Methylparaben	50mg	50mg	50mg
9.	Polyethyleneglycol 400	224mg	224mg	224mg
10.	Glycerin	260mg	260mg	260mg
11.	Ethanol	10ml	10ml	10ml
12.	Water	20ml	20ml	20ml

5. Evaluation of Film Forming Spray

5.1 pH

The pH of the prepared solution was measured at room temperature using pH paper and the change in color of the paper was observed. The color obtained was compared with the standard pH chart. The pH of the wound was around 7.4, bacteria need pH above 6

for their growth so the low pH accelerate wound healing process ^[18].

5.2 Volume per Spray

Ten sprays were actuated into a glass beaker and the volume per spray was estimated using analytical balance ^[19].

5.3 Drying Time/Film Forming Time

The solution is sprayed on any surface and allowed to dry at room temperature and the drying time was recorded by using digital stop watch, which was observed visually^[20].

5.4 Spray Angle

The sprays were actuated in the horizontal direction onto a whitepaper at a distance 15cm from the nozzle. The radius in triplicated from different direction^[21].

$$\text{Spray angle} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{l}{r} \right)$$

Where, l is distance of paper from the nozzle and r is average radius of circle.

5.5 Flexibility, Stickiness, and Washability

Flexibility of the film was determined by the simple method; the film was stretched in the two or three dimensions after the film was formed on the petri dish. If the film ruptured it is non flexible, if it is not, it is flexible. The ball of cotton wool is pressed against the formed film and the film was visually examined for fiber attached, the more the number of fibers attached to the film, stickier the film. Washability of the dried film was checked with water and graded as good (+++), moderate (++), poor (+)^[22].

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

1. Preparation of extracts by cold maceration method

The collected ethanolic extract was concentrated using a vacuum oven and further concentrated on a water bath. The final yield obtained was 10 g. The concentrated extract was subsequently subjected to antimicrobial evaluation.

2. Antimicrobial Studies

Antimicrobial activity was evaluated against representative bacterial and fungal strains, namely *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive bacteria), *Proteus vulgaris* (Gram-negative bacteria), and *Candida albicans* (fungi). These microorganisms were selected due to their clinical relevance in skin

and soft tissue infections and their common use in antimicrobial screening studies. The antimicrobial activity of the extract was evaluated at two different concentrations: one equivalent to the concentration of the standard drug and another at half of that concentration. The zones of inhibition produced by the standard drug (2 mg/ml), the test extract at low concentration (1 mg/ml), and the test extract at high concentration (2 mg/ml) were 31 mm, 14 mm, and 27 mm, respectively, against *Staphylococcus aureus*; 32.5 mm, 14.5 mm, and 26 mm, respectively, against *Proteus vulgaris*; and 28 mm, 13 mm, and 27 mm, respectively, against *Candida albicans*.

The ethanolic extract exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as fungi. The results suggest that the phytoconstituents present in *Tridax procumbens*, such as flavonoids, tannins, and alkaloids, contribute to its antimicrobial effect. Furthermore, the film-forming system of *Tridax procumbens* enhances topical retention, ensures uniform drug distribution, and provides sustained antimicrobial action, and is therefore expected to exhibit excellent wound-healing potential.

3. Optimization of excipients in film-forming spray

Initial placebo trials were carried out using hypromellose E-15 in ethanol, in which satisfactory film formation was observed along with minimal drying time due to the presence of the volatile solvent. Further trials were conducted using combinations with an aqueous phase. Film formation and drying time were considered critical evaluation parameters throughout the optimization process.

Hypromellose (HPMC E15) produces a highly viscous solution, which reduces sprayability. Therefore, combinations of polymers were investigated. Umar A. K. et al. reported that polymethacrylate (Eudragit S100) does not cause skin irritation^[21]. Since Eudragit S100 dissolves only at or above pH 7, the pH of water was adjusted to 7 prior to dissolving the polymer. During trials with Eudragit S100, the pH of the final formulation was identified as a critical optimization parameter, as precipitation occurred after two days. Additionally, in aqueous film-forming sprays containing Eudragit S100, the

drying time exceeded 10 minutes. As the acceptable drying time was 2 - 5 minutes [23], further trials were conducted with the addition of alcohol. The films formed using Eudragit S100 alone were brittle; therefore, further trials were performed using combinations with hypromellose (HPMC E15).

Placebo trials were also conducted using combinations of polymers such as polyvinyl alcohol, hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC, Klucel EXF), hypromellose (HPMC E15), and hypromellose (3 cPs) at various concentrations. Hypromellose (3 cPs) was used primarily to increase viscosity and to improve the mechanical strength of films containing HPMC E15.

All placebo trials were performed using various concentrations and combinations of polymers and solvents, and were evaluated for optimal drying time and film-forming ability. Glycerin was used as a humectant, while PEG 200 and PEG 400 were used as plasticizers to improve film plasticity.

Among the plasticizers tested, PEG 400 was found to be more effective than PEG 200. PEG 400 increased the volume delivered per spray of the film-forming solution, and the spray volume increased with increasing PEG 400 concentration. The covered spray area also increased with higher PEG 400 levels. This may be attributed to a decrease in vapour pressure due to the presence of PEG as a non-volatile solvent [21].

At the end of the placebo optimization trials, a solvent system consisting of 33.3% ethanol and 66.7% water was finalized for all polymer combinations, based on reduced drying time and good film-forming properties.

Among the placebo trials taken following concentrations were finalized on the basis of film formation, drying time and sprayability.

P11 - Eudragit-S 100 (1% w/v) with HPMC E-15 (3.33% w/v) and HPMC 3 cPs (0.33% w/v)

P12 - PVA (1.16% w/v) with HPMC E-15 (4% w/v) and HPMC 3cPs (0.33% w/v)

P13 - PVA (1.16% w/v) with HPC (Klucel EF) (3.33% w/v)

4. Formulation and evaluation of film-forming spray

The optimized placebo formulations (P 11, P12 and P13) were selected, and the crude extract dissolved in alcohol was incorporated to obtain film forming spray formulations F1, F2 and F3. The photo image of prepared film forming spray are given in Figure 1.

The developed film-forming spray formulations were evaluated for physicochemical and performance parameters including pH, volume per spray, drying time, spray angle, film flexibility, stickiness, and washability. The results are presented in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3: pH, Volume per spray, Drying time & Spray angle of Film Forming Spray

Parameters	F1	F2	F3
pH	6	6	6
Volume per spray	0.051ml	0.085ml	0.121ml
Drying time	3mins 30sec	4mins 20sec	4mins50sec
Spray angle	36.8°	43.5°	45.6°

Table 4: Flexibility, Stickiness, Washability of Film Forming Spray

Formulation Code	Film Flexibility	Stickiness	Washability
F1	+++	+++	+++
F2	++	++	+++
F3	++	++	+++

Good - (+++), Moderate - (++) , Poor - (+)

All formulations showed a pH of 6, indicating suitability for topical application with minimal risk of skin irritation. Formulation F1 delivered the lowest volume per actuation, indicating better control over dose uniformity and reduced formulation wastage. Formulation F3 showed the highest volume per spray, which may lead to excess application. Among the tested formulations, F1 demonstrated the shortest

drying time, which could be attributed to its lower polymer viscosity and faster solvent evaporation. The spray angle ranges from 36.8° to 45.6°. The film-forming spray F3 produced a wider dispersion pattern, while F1 showed a narrower spray angle, resulting in ensures targeted application and minimizes formulation wastage. The film-forming spray should have flexibility, strong film integrity and resistance to crack. The formulation should exhibit adequate stickiness to ensure good adhesion to the wound, while also allowing easy removal when required. Among the formulations, F1 exhibited all the required ideal characteristics for a film-forming spray.

Figure 1: Film Forming Spray

5. DISCUSSION

The scratches, cuts, abrasions, burns and other localized injuries with skin lesions, which can lead to contamination and subsequent infection. So far preventing the skin infections we need to adherence to therapy. The *Tridax Procumbens* plant was collected from the local area of the Madurai which was identified and washed to remove dirt and shade dried. Then powdered with mixer grinder and extraction was carried out with cold maceration method. The extract of *Tridax procumbens* was also analysed for the antimicrobial activity. Film forming spray has great potential for the treatment of various types of wounds (acute, chronic, complicated wounds). Such system affords to prolong the action of active substances, to prevent cross-contamination, and to ensure accelerated wound healing. This system offers many advantages over the other conventional topical preparations, because they can provide uniform drug distribution, increased bioavailability, lower incidence of irritation, continuous drug release.

To optimize the concentration of polymers, solvent, and plasticizers, in film forming spray, placebo trials at various concentration were taken. From this trial, based on the sprayability, film formation and drying time, concentration of solvents and plasticizer were finalized. Then according to the literature study, the film forming system was formulated with 5 % w/w of *Tridax procumbens* crude extract. Methyl paraben and Propyl paraben were used as preservatives. The prepared solution was evaluated for pH, drying time, volume per spray, spray angle, water washability, film flexibility and stickiness. Among the formulations, F1 exhibited all the required ideal characteristics for a film-forming spray. The film forming spray of all formulation (F1, F2, F3) showed neutral pH, and it has quick drying time, good thin film forming on the skin was observed. Among the formulations, F1 exhibited all the required ideal characteristics for a film-forming spray. These results fulfill the requirements for film forming spray for wound healing.

CONCLUSION

The overall conclusion of the study is that the optimized film forming topical spray of *Tridax Procumbens* Linn., for wound healing complies with all the requirements for film forming spray and has an excellent physical characteristic have been successfully formulated. Topical film forming spray of *Tridax procumbens* Linn., for wound healing has been developed for the first time and by further study of wound healing activity and clinical trials, the product could go for commercialization. The placebo film forming topical spray with all physical characteristics can be transformed as a platform for herbal drugs and upcoming new drugs.

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